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Shaping sustainable consumption practices: Changing consumers' habits through lifestyle changes and Extended Producer Responsibility schemes

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ABSTRACT

This paper studies Japan's consumer-side circular economy strategies, particularly focusing on the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) systems. The current low rates of EPR fees limit their effectiveness in promoting sustainable consumption and production practices. The study investigates how increasing EPR fees might alter Japanese household sufficiency behaviors under different lifestyle change assumptions. Using a socio-economic approach, it assesses how adjusting EPR fees can influence consumer behavior and environmental outcomes, contributing to a sustainable circular economy. The findings suggest higher EPR fees on energy-using durable goods encourage circular consumption, especially on consumers with strong cognitive intentions towards circular economy behaviors. Behavioural policies promoting environmental awareness are important enablers. In addition, the timing of EPR fee imposition (at acquisition vs. disposal) significantly affects the policy outcomes. While the policy can slow resource loops for some products, its impact on CO₂ emissions may be limited.

1. Introduction

Since the 1980s, Japan has pursued a circular production and consumption system to address environmental and public health challenges from rapid industrialization and economic growth (Ministry of the Environment, 2014; 2018). Limited landfill capacity in the 1990s led to illegal dumping and environmental crises, necessitating greater reliance on waste incineration and raising air pollution concerns. In response, Japan promoted the 3R principles—reduce, reuse, and recycle—through the 2000 Basic Act for Establishing a Sound Material-Cycle Society (Ministry of Environment, 2000), aiming to reduce resource consumption, waste generation, and CO₂ emissions. The urgency of this shift is highlighted by Japan's resource scarcity and recent economic security risks, such as those from the Ukraine war and China's export bans on strategic materials (e.g., rare earth elements) (Andrews-Speed and Hove, 2023).

Implementing the Sound Material-Cycle Society in Japan significantly decreased municipal waste, but this reduction has slowed since the 2010s. Between 2000 and 2010, waste generation decreased by 2 %

per year, but this rate dropped to 0.87 % per year between 2010 and 2020 (Mekonnen and Tokai, 2020). Despite high recycling rates for major home appliances thanks to the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) systems in place, the reuse of recycled materials in Japan remains uncertain as a significant portion is exported, hampering the transition to a circular economy (CE) (Yoshida et al., 2005; Okubo et al., 2016). Japan exports large quantities of recyclable waste, like plastic, paper, and metal scraps, due to less stringent environmental regulations in recipient countries (Yoshida et al., 2005; Okubo et al., 2016). Only 18 % of recycled plastic is used domestically, while the rest is exported (Plastic Waste Management Institute, 2022; Kumamaru and Takeuchi, 2023). According to Murakami et al. (2006), many recycled materials and second-hand appliances are shipped to Southeast Asia due to lower labor costs. The cyclical use rate of materials in Japan is 15 % (Ministry of Environment, 2000). The persistent high reliance on primary materials in Japan underscores the need for enhanced strategies to transition towards a more sustainable and circular model.

Under the Sound Material-Cycle Society, Japan has been implementing many EPR systems. However, current EPR fees for household

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appliances are too low to influence consumption and production choices (Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry, 2005; Association for Electric Home Appliances, 2024). Increasing EPR fees is essential for incentivizing green product design and conscious consumption behaviors (Hogg et al., 2020; Laubinger et al., 2021; Dalhammar et al., 2021; Micheaux and Aggeri, 2021; Lifset et al., 2023). Sachdeva et al. (2021) point out that EPR systems focus mainly on the minimization of end-of-life costs. To influence consumer choices, the fees could focus on the full life cycle of products by considering the overall social and environmental costs of the products as discussed by Hogg et al. (2020), Micheaux and Aggeri (2021), Sachdeva et al. (2021). Shifting fees to cover full lifecycle social and environmental costs remains a contested issue (OECD, 2016; Brown et al., 2023; Lifset et al., 2023), especially from stakeholders (Monier et al., 2014).

The success of CE policies such as EPR systems depends not only on policy support (Hartley et al., 2020) and innovations (Chauhan et al., 2022) but also on behavioral and lifestyle¹ changes (Kalmykova et al., 2016; Parajuly et al., 2020; Szilagyi et al., 2022; Shevchenko et al., 2023). The Ministry of Environment of Japan recognizes consumer lifestyles as crucial for a sustainable economy (Ministry of Environment, 2000; 2014). In 2012, the Act on Promotion Consumer Education was passed to foster sustainable consumption habits by encouraging reduced purchases and extending product lifespans through repair (Consumer Affairs Agency, 2022).

To promote sustainable consumption practices, Japan's vision could include consumer-focused strategies like Refuse, Rethink and Repair (Millar et al., 2019; Bongers and Casas, 2022). In this paper, we explore how much of the potential of EPR schemes can be unlocked through differentiated sufficiency behaviors. As Miliute-Plepiene et al. (2016) underlines, consumer behavior is influenced by many factors beyond techno-economic ones. We address this complexity by coupling a macroeconomic model (CIRCEE; Corbier et al., 2024) with a lifestyle model (LIFE; Pettifor et al., 2023) calibrated on Japanese data to assess the impact of EPR systems for energy-using goods on resource use, the economy, and CO₂ emissions across different low-carbon lifestyles. Energy-using goods are the focus because 50 % of their waste is illegally exported and dumped (Fuse et al., 2011) and only 15 % of recycled materials reenter the economy, hindering Japan's CE progress. Also, the latest IPCC report recognizes the important role that CE policies play in countries' transition to net zero emissions in the long run. EPR fees may introduce certain trade-offs between different sustainable strategies. They may trigger rebound effects—for instance, by encouraging less energy-efficient repairs over new efficient products (Boldoczki et al., 2021; Glöser-Chahoud et al., 2021) increasing CO₂ emissions—which CIRCEE considers.

2. Literature review

We survey the literature on the use of economic modeling to study the socioeconomic and resource impact of CE policies. As highlighted by Parajuly et al. (2020), much of the literature on the CE has focused more on production-side strategies than on the role of consumers in promoting the CE. Using CGE models, Masui (2005), Okushima and Yamashita (2005) show that optimal waste management policies in Japan are driven by R&D investment in waste treatment technologies (Masui, 2005) and place emphasis on the effectiveness of industrial waste taxes without hampering growth (Okushima and Yamashita, 2005). Pittel et al. (2010) developed an analytical general equilibrium model demonstrating that waste markets and subsidies can optimize recycling under market failures. Similarly, Kinnaman and Yokoo (2011), Yokoo and Kinnaman (2013) show analytically that e-waste taxes and subsidies can lead to global economic efficiency in developing countries. Using a

Ramsey-type model, Akimoto and Futagami (2018) argue that consumption taxes and subsidies can facilitate the transition towards a CE. Lafforgue and Rouge (2019), employing a dynamic general equilibrium model, found that reducing recycling costs through technological advances can enhance economic circularity in the EU-27. Bongers and Casas (2022), also using a dynamic general equilibrium model, explore the optimal path for R&D investments in recycling technologies. Nechifor et al. (2020) assess the significant impact of increased recycling incentives on China's GDP through the ENGAGE-materials model. Lahcen et al. (2022), using a supply-chain general equilibrium model for Belgium's Coca Cola firm, show that public perception of circular products as good substitutes for conventional products is crucial for policy success. Brusselaers et al. (2022), using a CGE model for Belgium, find that expansionary fiscal policies boost household participation in circular activities.

Other studies focus on extending product lifetimes. Zhou and Smulders (2021) discuss the potential crowding-out effect of reuse and refurbishment on innovations in green product design via an endogenous growth model. Studies such as Oguchi and Fuse (2015), Nakamoto and Kagawa (2018), Nishijima et al. (2020) emphasize the trade-off between repairing and purchasing new goods concerning energy consumption and product longevity in Japan.

While these studies are innovative, most overlook consumer-side CE strategies and the significance of households with different sufficiency behaviors. The CE drive new consumption behaviors. Pettifor et al. (2023) show that shifting to a low-carbon lifestyle involves modifying several aspects of daily activities, driven by low-carbon cognition and shaped by social and material contexts. Exploring lifestyle heterogeneity can also help to understand different responses to policy incentives.

A limited strand of literature focus on the role of consumer participation in driving the demand for circularity at the micro-level. A strand of the literature shows the importance of cognitive and contextual drivers in shaping consumer behaviors toward circularity. Kumar (2019) finds that attitude, perceived control, subjective norms, individual responsibility and material context influence consumer behaviors related to e-waste disposal. Piscicelli et al. (2018) discuss the importance of consumer values priorities and orientations for the acceptance and the success of the sharing economy. Van Weelden et al. (2016) show that personal and contextual factors shape the consumers behaviors on the decision to refurbish products. Abbey et al. (2015a) study consumer perceptions of remanufactured/refurbished consumer goods, pointing out that price discounts and quality perceptions positively affect these goods. Another strand of the literature shows the importance of barriers to acceptance of CE strategies. Maitre-Ekern and Dalhammar (2019) identify the lack of awareness and interest in CE strategies as behavioral barriers, market and legal barriers to acceptance of CE strategies, such as the lack of products information. According to Linder et al. (2018), providing the right information to consumers can influence their pro-environmental behaviors in recycling food waste in Sweden. Van Weelden et al. (2016) show that consumers avoid refurbished mobile phones due to a lack of awareness and perceived risks.

3. Methodology

The model CIRCEE of Corbier et al. (2024) is a dynamic general equilibrium model with resource/stock flow consistency (see Fig. 1), soft-linked to the LIFE model (Pettifor et al., 2023) and to the Integrated Assessment Model (IAM) WITCH (Emmerling et al., 2016). The model includes microeconomic foundations, industrial ecology concepts and households' lifestyle heterogeneity. For the mathematical description of CIRCEE, see Appendix A.

Sufficiency behaviors and budget constraints differ among three households (see Appendix C for a description of lifestyles in CIRCEE):

- 'Low-carbon' are driven by environmental beliefs with strong low-carbon cognitions and more enabling material and social contexts.

¹ Lifestyle is defined as the interplay between cognitions and behavior in specific material and social contexts.

Fig. 1. CIRCEE graphical representation.

- ‘Cautious’ have weak cognitive drivers, moderate wealth and lacks willingness to engage in low-carbon behavior driven by their passive view on climate change.
- ‘Constrained’ have weak low-carbon cognitions, less enabling material and social context, and their need to save money leads them to involuntarily adopt a low-carbon lifestyle.

Changes in sufficiency behaviors for households have a direct impact on their consumption decisions for conventional/brand-new energy-using goods and circular substitutes (sharing and repair). A higher engagement in sufficiency behaviors results in lower ownership rates of energy-using goods (see Eq. (A19) of Appendix A).

Households consume energy services, semi-durable goods (e.g. furniture and clothing) and nondurable goods (e.g. food and packaging) (Fig. 1 and Eq. (A9) of Appendix A). Energy services, such as “mobility”, are either provided by a sharing market or produced at home (Eq. (A10) in Appendix A). They refer to the services provided by energy via the use of energy-using goods (Eq. (A11) in Appendix A). Households produce energy services, e.g. “mobility”, at home by owning durable goods, e.g. a car, and consuming efficient energy (in joules). Efficient energy relates to energy effectively used to produce an energy service. The evolution of energy efficiency is calibrated from WITCH. The sharing firm rents labor and energy-using goods from households during the time they are not using it for their own production of energy services at home and buys energy to produce a shared energy service. Households also have the option to repair part of their energy-using goods stock instead of purchasing new goods (Eq. (A19) of Appendix A).

4. Data and scenarios

4.1. Extended producer responsibility schemes in Japan

Japan has well-developed EPR schemes covering cars, household appliances and packaging. Currently, EPR fees for household electric appliances and automobiles in Japan are too low compared to the overall purchase price of these products to foster sustainable consumption behaviors (see Table 1).

CIRCEE treats all energy-using goods as a single aggregated good to catch the main transmission channels of EPR schemes. We recognize that

Table 1

EPR schemes by product category and related recycling fees in Japan. Sources: OECD (2016), Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (2005), Japan Portable Rechargeable Battery Recycling Center:(2024)., Association for Electric Home Appliances (2024).

Product	Cost Allocation	Timing	Recycling Fee (JPY/unit)
Refrigerators	Consumers	At disposal	3740–6149
Washing Machines	Consumers	At disposal	2530–3300
Air Conditioners	Consumers	At disposal	990–2000
Televisions	Consumers	At disposal	1320–3700
Small Home Appliances	Consumers	At disposal	0
Cars	Consumers	At acquisition	6000–18,000
Rechargeable batteries	Producers	–	–
Packaging	Producers (Specified business entity)	At disposal	up to 62 JPY/kg

consumers may respond differently to EPR fees depending on the specific good category. When the fee is calculated as a percentage of the final price of a good, households may show reduced sensitivity towards price hikes on affordable goods in the face of increased EPR fees. In addition, repair costs for various products differ significantly due to factors like usage intensity, product complexity, spare parts availability and cost. According to [Svensson-Hoglund et al. \(2021\)](#), [McCullough \(2009\)](#), goods linked to conspicuous consumption are typically replaced instead of repaired when their replacement cost is perceived as closer to the repair cost.

4.2. Scenarios

In Japan, the recycling fee for automobiles is paid at the time of purchase, while for home appliances, it is paid at the time of disposal ([Shinkuma, 2007](#)). Drawing on [Menell \(1990\)](#), [Fullerton and Kinnaman \(1995\)](#), [Kinokuni et al. \(2021\)](#), we explore how these different timings of EPR fees guide consumption choices, with an application to Japan. [Menell \(1990\)](#) shows that including a disposal fee in the retail price increases consumer awareness of disposal costs. Analytical models by [Fullerton and Kinnaman \(1995\)](#), [Kinokuni et al. \(2021\)](#) further show that an upfront disposal fee is effective in deterring illegal disposal—unless waste and dumping taxes are imposed. In Japan, [Hotta et al. \(2014\)](#) recommend an EPR fee at purchase to prevent illegal dumping and export of electronic waste, a view supported by stakeholder surveys [Tasaki et al. \(2015\)](#) that favor integrating end-of-life management costs into product prices.

EPR fees can also differ as to whether they are “visible”, that is displayed at the time of purchase, or “hidden”. As highlighted by [Chetty et al. \(2009\)](#), [Bordalo et al. \(2013\)](#) visible fees can influence consumer behavior more strongly because they make the cost more apparent to consumers. This can particularly influence ‘Low-carbon’ households, by aligning with their value orientation towards sustainable consumption choices. In contrast, hidden fees could fail to leverage the behavioral impact of buying new ([Gabaix et al., 2006](#)). While our model masks individual behavioral nuances like fee saliency, incorporating a contra-factual with hidden fees would yield similar consumption decisions through the change in relative prices.

In addition, we assume two policy scenarios for the evolution of the EPR fee: (i) a current policy scenario and (ii) a policy scenario in which the EPR fee reaches 17 % of the final price of energy-using goods by 2050. We find through numerical exploration that setting the fee above 17 % with lifestyle changes leads to model instability. From a policy perspective, 17 % is sufficiently large to induce meaningful shifts in repair behavior. Also, this value is grounded in the work of [Hogg et al. \(2020\)](#), [Micheaux and Aggeri \(2021\)](#) and the French Circular Economy Law, which suggest that the fee should increase up to a maximum of 20 % of the product’s final price.

Finally, we model sufficiency behavior as a cognitively-driven and contextually-driven process, reflecting how households may adopt sufficiency practices supported by Japan’s Act on the Promotion of Consumer Education (see [Table 2](#)). This important distinction acknowledges heterogeneity in the drivers of low-carbon lifestyles between enabled households, for whom choice is purposeful and intentional, and households for whom consumption activity is driven by inequalities in affordability, education, and access to infrastructure and services ([Shigetomi et al., 2020](#); [Kaaronen and Strelkovskii, 2020](#); [Kukowski and Garnett, 2024](#)).

4.3. Data

The model parameters are calibrated using Japanese national statistics, the Japan Industrial Productivity (JIP) Database 2021 from RIETI, the GLORIA database from [Lenzen et al. \(2017, 2022\)](#), OECD database, literature studies, online surveys and expert consensus approaches. Detailed information about the calibration process is available

in Appendix B.

5. Results

5.1. The timing of the EPR fees is an important factor to consider in the design of EPR schemes

Implementing EPR fees effectively reduces long-term demand for these goods (graph a. of [Fig. 2](#)). When the EPR fee is charged at acquisition rather than at disposal, it has a more significant impact on reducing overall demand for energy-using goods in the long-run. Because of the discount factor ($\beta = 0.98573$), households value current damages more than future damages, leading to increased sensitivity to current income fluctuations. For new acquisitions in date t , a fee paid at the time of disposal affects the income of households at the date of disposal of the good, i.e. at future dates. Also, when the fee is paid at disposal, households consider the possibility of selling them before disposal to avoid paying the fee, overall decreasing the impact of the fee on future income. In contrast, an EPR fee paid at acquisition impacts current income as the fee is paid at the date of purchase, lowering the total income available for the consumption of other goods. For example, purchasing a new car will impact their current income in the acquisition scenario more than the disposal scenario because more income is allocated for the purchase of the car.

Up to 2035, energy-using goods purchases are higher in the acquisition version than the disposal version for two main reasons:

- 1. Energy Efficiency Gains:** Under current climate policies for the scenario SSP2, most energy efficiency gains are realized before 2035, reducing the overall user cost of energy-using goods and incentivizing households to buy more new energy-efficient goods in the acquisition version compared to the disposal version of the fee. After 2035, the dynamics of both scenario start diverging significantly as the benefit of operating a more energy-efficient good is lower than the increase in the cost of acquisition of the good because of the higher EPR fee.
- 2. Timing of Fees:** At the date of implementation of the policy (2025), households have an existing stock of energy-using durable goods that will be disposed of in later periods, at a maximum of 2035 for the acquisitions of goods in 2024. An increase in disposal fees negatively affects the user cost of energy-using goods currently in use in the year 2025 that will soon be disposed of, impacting current income as households must pay an unforeseen fee on previously purchased durable goods. In contrast, in the acquisition version, the user cost of energy-using goods in use in 2025 is not impacted by the fee since they were purchased previously. After the year 2035, dynamics begin to change as the old stock of durable goods is fully disposed of.

Higher EPR fees induces a greater shift toward circular-related consumption activities and non-energy services (graphs b., c. and d. of [Fig. 2](#)). Compared to current policy, households substitute new purchases with repairs and substitute home-produced energy services with shared ones, particularly when the fee is charged at acquisition. Up to 2035, the decrease in shared energy services in the acquisition version is driven by higher purchases of energy-using goods due to the two effects discussed above, prompting households to consume energy services at home. When the EPR fee is charged at disposal, the repairing economy is relatively less promoted. If households choose to repair their car instead of disposing of it immediately, this postpones disposal to a later period when the associated fee is higher. Thus, it incentivizes households to buy new and use sharing services to avoid the payment of higher future disposal fee. Overall, EPR fees can create synergies among different CE strategies when implemented at acquisition, but also trade-offs between sufficiency and repairing when implemented at disposal.

The ease to substitute from brand new goods to repaired goods, as reflected by the elasticity of substitution (see Eq. (A19) in Appendix A),

Table 2

Scenarios. ‘LowCarbonCogn’ denotes that sufficiency behavior is cognitively driven, motivated by strong low-carbon cognitions, as an intentional activity. ‘Low-carbon’ households engage intentionally in sufficiency behaviors in accordance with low-carbon values and beliefs. ‘NeedSaveMoney’ denotes sufficiency behavior that is contextually driven, motivated by the need to save money, as an unintentional activity. ‘Constrained’ households engage in sufficiency behavior to save money. ‘None’ denotes sufficiency behavior that is homogeneous across the three types of households and not driven by any lifestyle characteristics. The ‘LowCarbonCogn’ and ‘NeedSaveMoney’ variants allow us to explore whether households driven by low-carbon cognitions act accordingly.

Policy Design	Acquisition			Disposal		
	<i>EPR fee included in final price of goods</i>			<i>EPR fee is paid at the date of disposal of goods</i>		
EPR increase in 2025	Increase annually from 4.1 % to 17 %			Increase annually from 4.1 % to 17 %		
Sufficiency Driver	.LowCarbonCogn	.NeedSaveMoney	.None	.LowCarbonCogn	.NeedSaveMoney	.None

can impact the overall results. The sensitivity analysis performed in Supplementary Materials (Figs. B2 and B3 of Appendix B) highlights that the ease of substituting repairs is crucial when implementing fiscal incentives to encourage households to shift toward circular services. Factors such as the availability of spare parts and repair quality influence this decision.

5.2. Lifestyles changes are antecedent to EPR schemes

Lifestyle changes support the success of EPR policies, particularly in the ‘LowCarbonCogn’ variant, driven by the proactive behavior of

‘Low-carbon’ households who represent more than 60 % of the population. ‘LowCarbonCogn’ yields the best outcomes with fewer energy-using good purchases and higher consumption of circular services (graphs a., b. and d. of Figs. 2 and 3). Driven by their passive low-carbon intentions, ‘Cautious’ and ‘Constrained’ households engage less in sufficiency behavior than in the other sufficiency variants (graphs b. and c. of Fig. 3). Thus, the impact of weak intentions towards sufficiency in the consumption of energy-using goods is stronger than the price effect from higher EPR fees. Also, the higher stock of energy-using goods owned by ‘Constrained’ and ‘Cautious’ households lead to relatively more goods being repaired in the ‘LowCarbonCogn’ variant (graphs e. and f. of

Fig. 2. Graph a. shows the evolution of new durable goods acquisitions in deviation from current policy (%). Graph b. shows the evolution of repair to new acquisitions of durable goods ratio in deviation from current policy (%). Graph c. shows the evolution of non-energy services consumption to energy services consumption ratio in deviation from current policy (%). Graph d. shows the evolution of shared to home-produced energy services ratio in deviation from current policy (%). There are two versions of the model for the implementation of the EPR fee: (i) the fee is paid at the point of acquisition (solid line) and (ii) the fee is paid at the date of disposal (dashed line). The engagement in sufficiency behavior of the three types of households in CIRCEE - namely, ‘Low-carbon’, ‘Cautious’ and ‘Constrained’ - is approached via three variants: (i) sufficiency behaviors are homogeneous across the three types of households and not driven by any lifestyle characteristics (purple), (ii) sufficiency behavior is driven by low-carbon cognitions (voluntary engagement) (green) and (iii) sufficiency behavior is driven by the need to save money (involuntary engagement) (blue). Source: CIRCEE-LIFE simulations.

Fig. 3. Graphs a–c. show the evolution of new durable goods acquisitions for each lifestyle type in deviation from year 2025 (%). Graphs d., e. and f. show the evolution of repair to new acquisitions of durable goods ratio for each lifestyle type in deviation from year 2025 (%). Graphs g., h. and i. show the evolution of shared to home-produced energy services ratio for each lifestyle type in deviation from year 2025 (%). There are two versions of the model for the implementation of the EPR fee: (i) the fee is paid at the point of acquisition (solid lines) and (ii) the fee is paid at the date of disposal (dashed lines). The engagement into sufficiency behavior of the three types of households in CIRCEE - namely, 'Low-carbon', 'Cautious' and 'Constrained' – is approached via three variants: (i) sufficiency behaviors are homogeneous across the three types of households and not driven by any lifestyle characteristics (purple), (ii) sufficiency behavior is driven by low-carbon cognitions (voluntary engagement) (green) and (iii) sufficiency behavior is driven by the need to save money (involuntary engagement) (blue). Source: CIRCEE-LIFE simulations.

Fig. 3). This suggests that overall the combined lifestyle conditions of low-cost and passive intentions are stronger drivers of sufficiency behaviors, compared to strong intentions and higher price.

In the 'NeedSaveMoney' variant, 'Constrained' households reduce durable goods acquisitions and engages in circular services more than in the 'None' variant because it mobilises lifestyle types with weak intentions towards sufficiency as a pro-environmental activity. The greater responsiveness of 'Constrained' households to policy changes is attributed to liquidity constraints that make them relatively more sensitive to current income changes. 'Cautious' households also reduce acquisitions as they tend to have fewer household members, and more likely to be 'empty nesters'. The 'Low-carbon' household engages less in sufficiency behavior and engages relatively less in circular-related services.

Compared to the 'None' variant, sufficiency behaviors coupled with economic incentives in the 'LowCarbonCogn' variant decrease the purchase of energy-using goods of the 'Low-carbon' household by approximately 7 percentage point in 2050. While, in the 'SaveMoney' variant, sufficiency behaviors coupled with economic incentives decrease the purchase of energy-using goods of the 'Constrained'

household by approximately 11.5 percentage point in 2050. Sufficiency behaviors are more likely to be driven by a need to save money than to save the environment.

5.3. Enhanced resource security and waste generation reduction amid substitution dynamics

The dynamics of the in-use stock of durable goods follow those of durable goods acquisitions (graph a. of Figs. 2 and 4). When the EPR fee is charged at acquisition, the policy yields the best outcomes in terms of material needs reductions thanks to lower energy-using goods acquisitions and a higher substitution towards circular-related services. Material imports and gross additions to in-use stocks (graphs b. and a. of Fig. 4) are lower due to reduced material needs to produce energy-using goods. When the EPR fee is charged at disposal, higher material needs, and in-use stocks result from higher durable goods acquisitions and a greater shift towards non-energy services consumption. Overall, resource security improves in the EPR policy scenario.

When sufficiency behaviors are driven by the need to save money,

Fig. 4. Graph a. shows the deviation of gross additions to the in-use stocks of semi-durable goods, durable goods and capital goods from current policy scenario by 2050 in Million tonnes. Graph b. shows the deviation of total material imports from current policy scenario by 2050 in Million tonnes per year. Graphs c. and d. show the deviation of industrial and municipal waste from current policy scenario by 2050 in Million tonnes per year. Graph e. and f. show the deviation of households' and economic activities' final energy use from current policy scenario by 2050 in EJ per year. Graph g. shows the deviation of CO₂ emissions for the economy but the incineration sector (yellow) and incineration sector (purple) from current policy scenario by 2050 in MtCO₂ per year. Graph a. and Graph f. axis legends read as follows: 'Acq.' corresponds to a fee imposed at the point of acquisition, 'Disp.' corresponds to a fee imposed at the point of disposal, '.None' corresponds to no sufficiency behavior drivers, '.LowCarbonCogn' corresponds to sufficiency behavior driven by low-carbon cognitions and '.SaveMoney' corresponds to sufficiency behavior driven by the need to save money. Source: CIRCEE-LIFE simulations.

EPR fees have less beneficial outcomes due to higher material needs from the substitution towards non-energy services,² higher capital investments from higher demand of consumption goods, and increased durable goods acquisitions compared to when sufficiency behaviors are driven by low-carbon cognitions.

Municipal waste flows are lower in the EPR policy scenario compared to the current policy scenario (graphs c. and d. of Fig. 4). By 2050, municipal waste generation is 3 Mt lower than the current policy scenario when the EPR fee is charged at acquisition with sufficiency behaviors, and 2 Mt lower when the EPR fee is charged at disposal with sufficiency behaviors. Also, the rebalancing of the consumption basket in favor of non-energy services in all policy and sufficiency variants (graph c. of Fig. 2) increases the disposal of non-durable and semi-durable goods, and partially offsets the initial reduction in municipal waste from lower energy-using durable goods disposal.

The impact on industrial waste depends on the sufficiency variant (graph d. of Fig. 4.). The EPR fee charged at acquisition fosters the best outcomes in terms of waste reduction driven by a lower production of energy-using goods. The '.LowCarbonCogn' variant shows the greatest reduction due to lower goods demand at the aggregate level. In the '.SaveMoney' variant, industrial waste increases compared to current policy due to higher demand of consumption goods and higher capital needs, increasing residual waste generation and the disposal of capital machinery and equipment.

5.4. Balancing energy efficiency gains, CO₂ emission reductions and the role of substitution mechanisms

Household energy use is lower by, at most, 0.06 EJ in 2050 compared to current policy when the fee is imposed at acquisition (graph e. of Fig. 4). While households purchase fewer brand-new energy-efficient goods, they do not reduce their needs for energy services. Instead, they maintain their energy services consumption by repairing and continuing to use less efficient goods, as well as by shifting toward sharing services. Also, the higher shift towards repairing and thus the energy consumption from the service of older and less energy-efficient goods mitigate the impact of the policy on the energy needs of the economy compared to when the fee is charged at disposal. When the fee is charged at disposal, the higher reduction in household energy use (0.075 EJ) is driven by higher consumption of shared energy services, the shift towards non-energy services, and higher energy efficiency because of a lower share of less energy-efficient (repaired) goods³ in the total stock compared to when the fee is charged at acquisition.

The EPR fee charged at acquisition produces the most significant reduction in CO₂ emissions (graph g. of Fig. 4), largely due to decreased production of energy-using goods and reduced consumption of energy services. The overall impact on CO₂ emissions is attenuated by higher energy needs in energy-intensive sectors producing non-durable and semi-durable goods, and shared services because of consumption substitution mechanisms (graph f. of Fig. 4). In addition, in Japan, 75 % of municipal waste and 45 % of industrial waste are incinerated every year (Fig. D11 in Appendix D). The CO₂ emissions from lower waste incineration enhances the positive environmental outcome of EPR policies. In the acquisition scenario with '.LowCarbonCogn' variant, the reduction of CO₂ emissions compared to a current policy scenario is approximately 7 MtCO₂ in 2050, with the incineration sector accounting for approximately 20 % of the reduction. In absolute levels, the long-run dynamics of CO₂ emissions are primarily driven by energy efficiency gains (Fig. D10 in Appendix D).

² Non-durable goods and semi-durable goods represent approximately 85% of material needs to produce consumption goods in Japan.

³ In CIRCEE, repair goods are assumed to have the energy efficiency of date (t-1), while new goods have the energy efficiency of date (t).

6. Discussion

6.1. Policy implications

Japan's 20-year EPR experience has advanced recycling in automotive and electronic sectors. For cars, despite roughly 4 million new registrations annually (JAMA Active-Matrix Database System)—implying limited impact on sustainable consumption—about 80 % of end-of-life vehicles are recycled, although some are exported to lower-income countries Brown et al. (2023). Recycling rates for electrical and electronic equipment increased by 20 percentage points over 15 years OECD (2016), yet nearly half of the waste bypasses official channels, with 30 % reaching second-hand markets or scrap. The results of the paper highlight several policy implications that can guide future decisions on advancing EPR schemes. EPR fees on energy-using goods can drive circular consumption when paired with behavioral responses that emphasize environmental benefits and reduce resource demand.

Raising the cost of new acquisitions via EPR fees encourages households to adopt circular services like repair and sharing, fostering synergies among R strategies. EPR fees can be integrated with other CE policies, such as fiscal incentives for repair, to create an integrated policy mix. For example, Reimann (2024) demonstrates the value of repair subsidies, while McCollough (2009) stresses lowering repair costs relative to replacements. Moreover, Nishijima et al. (2020) shows that higher prices paired with enhanced durability promote longer product use.

Timing is crucial for policy design. Charged at acquisition, EPR fees offer immediate incentives for circular practices, reducing waste and material demands more effectively than fees at disposal. Brusselsaers et al. (2022) finds that expansionary fiscal policies boost household participation in circular activities, and Hotta et al. (2014) recommends EPR fees at acquisition in Japan to deter illegal dumping and waste exports, as also supported analytically by Menell (1990), Fullerton and Kinnaman (1995), Kinokuni et al. (2021).

Nevertheless, consumer substitution mechanisms may reduce environmental benefits. While higher EPR fees limit durable goods stock growth and waste generation, they may shift demand toward more resource-intensive semi-durable or non-durable goods—which represent over 85 % of consumption expenses and material demand in Japan—and undermine the initial positive effects on waste generation. In addition, increased use of sharing services and the use of less efficient repaired goods can further raise energy requirements, partially offsetting CO₂ emission savings.

The success of EPR fees is also influenced by household lifestyles. Consumers with strong low-carbon cognitions respond better, highlighting the need for policies that strengthen low-carbon cognitive values. Since responses vary across cognitive perceptions, social and material contexts (Allcott, 2011; Wilson and Dowlatabadi, 2007), policies must incorporate these underlying factors that influence circular consumption practices. Households driven by low-carbon cognitions will be crucial for the success of the CE, as illustrated by the '.LowCarbonCogn' variant, in high-income countries. Contextually driven households, which represent a larger share of the population in low-income countries, also play a significant role in promoting CE strategies in these regions, as illustrated by the '.SaveMoney' variant. In the literature, Pereira et al. (2024) emphasizes the role of green marketing education, and Linder et al. (2018), Reynolds et al. (2024) stress the importance of better information and education for encouraging circular behavior. Additionally, Abbey et al. (2015b), Nishijima et al. (2020) suggest potential synergies between economic and behavioral strategies, and Parajuly et al. (2020), Cao et al. (2018) confirm that economic incentives and awareness campaigns together stimulate repair.

The environmental benefits of CE strategies should not be taken for granted. EPR fees at acquisition can reduce municipal and industrial waste, energy consumption, and CO₂ emissions. However, rebound

effects may arise if households use less efficient repairs or switch to more resource-intensive goods in their production process. Studies (Oguchi and Fuse, 2015; Nakamoto and Kagawa, 2018; Nishijima et al., 2020) highlight these trade-offs between repairing and buying new in Japan, and Lahcen et al. (2022) show that repairs do not always lower life-cycle energy, and factors such as product's durability, the quality of repair and the replacement product's energy efficiency are key drivers of the results. To mitigate these effects, policies should pair repair incentives with measures to improve energy efficiency of repaired goods (Jerome et al., 2023).

Japan's reliance on incineration for over two-thirds of its waste treatment means that reduced waste through higher EPR fees can lower CO₂ emissions—a benefit that may extend to other countries.

Finally, aligning EPR fees with product performance standards promotes durability, repairability, and recyclability. Such fees nudge consumers toward eco-friendly choices and encourage greener designs (OECD, 2016). High fees drive green product innovation (Lindhqvist and Lifset, 2003; Gui et al., 2013), though, as Shinkuma (2007) notes, durability also depends on consumer maintenance. Thus, combining economic incentives, education, standards—and modulated fees based on design features (Gui et al., 2013)—can reinforce design-for-environment efforts. This integrated approach ensures that environmental and economic benefits reinforce each other in promoting a CE.

6.2. Limitations and further research

Since the introduction of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) policies in Japan, the technological landscape has undergone significant changes. The “twin transition” is reshaping communication and consumption patterns, highlighting the need for EPR systems to evolve accordingly.

On the digital side, rapid technological developments in the automotive and information and communication technology (ICT) sectors have accelerated product replacement cycles, spurred by aggressive marketing strategies and planned obsolescence (Dechezleprêtre et al., 2023). Digital innovation has also enabled new business models, such as shared mobility services, further altering the traditional life-cycle of products. However, alongside these technological shifts, the environmental twin of the transition has been equally influential, particularly for green product design.

Moreover, digital technological changes influencing household purchasing behaviors must be considered when designing EPR schemes. We do not look at how different digitalization scenarios can enable low-carbon cognitions and give more opportunity to engage into circular behaviors (Hedberg and Sipka, 2021; Pettifor et al., 2024). Also, the rise of e-commerce and online sales from over-seas can bypass EPR channels (Hilton et al., 2019), potentially undermining their effectiveness. This issue is particularly significant for goods with high EPR fees, as consumers may be incentivized to purchase online from overseas retailers to free ride the EPR system. Addressing this loophole requires further research to ensure that EPR systems remain robust in the face of evolving consumer behaviors and market dynamics.

On the environmental side, policymakers and manufacturers are rethinking product life-cycles, which emphasizes the importance of designing products for durability, repairability, and recyclability. By adjusting EPR fees, governments can create incentives for manufacturers to innovate in green product design, which we do not address in CIRCEE. EPR targets must adapt to evolving market conditions and technologies to effectively promote a CE (OECD, 2016). For example, targeted EPR schemes for fuel-based vehicles can facilitate the transition to electric vehicles as highlighted by recent studies (Watkins and Farmer, 2023). Moreover, technological advancements often rely on strategic materials that are controlled by a limited number of suppliers and highlights the importance of EPR schemes in addressing resource dependencies resulting from technological innovations.

7. Conclusion

We assess the impact of EPR fees on sufficiency behaviors under different lifestyle change assumptions, as well as on socioeconomic, CO₂ emissions, and resource outcomes. Our findings suggest that incorporating consumer behavior and heterogeneous lifestyles into policy design, along-side producer responsibility, can significantly enhance EPR outcomes. By integrating targeted education, strong economic incentives, and appropriate product standards, countries can achieve significant reductions in waste generation, resource use, and CO₂ emissions, well beyond the Japanese context.

Although EPR policies worldwide have often focused on recyclability and eco-design standards, countries with high reliance on primary resources, high waste generation and incineration (e.g., Japan, EU countries) should widen the Reduce-Reuse-Recycle framework to include other strategies aimed at promoting sustainable consumption practices. Higher and “visible” EPR fees have the potential to effectively promote sustainable consumption behaviors. Policymakers should consider additional factors in the design of EPR schemes. Imposing fees at acquisition rather than disposal strengthens incentives for waste reduction and resource use. However, rebound effects—like increased reliance on less energy-efficient repairs—highlight the need for complementary measures such as improving the energy efficiency of repaired goods.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Darius Corbier: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Hazel Pettifor:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Maureen Agnew:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Miyuki Nagashima:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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